

Water Data Portals: An Annotated List

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The attached list contains links to web portals and/or websites with data or links to data on water resources (including flow, water quality and integrated water resources management). This list is not intended to be comprehensive. Additions or notifications of dead links can be sent to janet.hering@eawag.ch.

Entries are listed alphabetically. Inclusion on this list does not imply any endorsement of data quality. All websites last accessed on April 5, 2017.

name	link	description (taken or adapted from the website)
CEH Data	http://www.ceh.ac.uk/data	Long-term, national-scale data provided by the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UK)
CUAHSI Data Services	https://www.cuahsi.org/dataservices	Data provided by the Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science (US)
earth2Observe Water Cycle Integrator (WCI)	https://wci.earth2observe.eu/	The WCI portal takes data that you select and plots it on a map to help you analyse, export and share it.
Eawag NADUF	http://www.eawag.ch/en/department/wut/main-focus/chemistry-of-water-resources/naduf/	Long term data series collected as part of the program "National Long-Term Surveillance of Swiss Rivers" (NADUF).
European Environment Agency Water Data Centre	http://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/water/dc	European entry point for water related data as part of the Water Information System for Europe (WISE).
FAO Aquastat	http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/main/index.stm	FAO's global water information system, developed by the Land and Water Division
Freshwater Information Platform	http://www.freshwaterplatform.eu/	A platform offering links to data, maps, tools and other resources relating to freshwater resources and their biodiversity.
GEOSS portal	http://www.geoportal.org/	Entry point for earth observation data implemented and operated by the European Space Agency. <i>(Note that most data are not water-related.)</i>
Global Environmental Monitoring System – Water	http://web.unep.org/gemswater/	GEMS/Water works to: ensure water quality data flows from a world-wide network, maintain the global water quality database (GEMStat), and enable countries to deliver authoritative data through capacity development.
Global Mercury Observation System	http://www.gmos.eu/sdi/	The GMOS Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) was developed in order to assure a timely and up-to-date sharing of information on mercury in the environment, including humans. <i>(Note that most data are not water-related.)</i>

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Global Rivers Observatory	http://www.globalrivers.org/	The Global Rivers Observatory (led by the Woods Hole Research Center and the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution) investigates river chemistry in Earth's most significant river systems. It is active in 18 watersheds around the world and measures the chemical composition of rivers near their entry points to the ocean.
Groundwater Assessment Platform	http://www.gapmaps.org/gap.protected/	Mapping and information platform for geogenic groundwater contamination
HydroLAKES	http://www.hydrosheds.org/page/hydrolakes	A database provided by WWF that seeks to provide shoreline polygons for all global lakes with a surface area of at least 10 ha with some ancillary data.
Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE)	http://hypeweb.smhi.se/	Modeled Open Data for inspection and free download from multi-basin and large-scale applications of the HYPE model world-wide provided by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute.
HydroSHEDS (Hydrological data and maps based on Shuttle Elevation Derivatives at multiple Scales)	http://www.hydrosheds.org/	HydroSHEDS is a mapping product that provides hydrographic information for regional and global-scale applications in a consistent format. It offers a suite of geo-referenced data sets (vector & raster) at various scales, including river networks, watershed boundaries, drainage directions, and flow accumulations. HydroSHEDS is based on high-resolution elevation data obtained during a Space Shuttle flight for NASA's Shuttle Radar Topography Mission.
International Hydrological Programme's Water Information Network System	http://ihp-wins.unesco.org/	Entry point to water resources and data from UNESCO's International Hydrological Programme
IWMI Water Data Portal	http://waterdata.iwmi.org/	Entry point provided by the International Water Management Institute for a large amount of data related to water and agriculture, including meteorological, hydrological, socio-economic, spatial data layer, satellite images as well as hydrological model setups.
IWRM Data Portal (UNEP-DHI)	http://iwrmdataportal.unepdhi.org/	This data portal offers a comprehensive collection of national IWRM implementation progress data drawn from two global country IWRM progress surveys.
Joint Research Centre Water Portal	http://water.jrc.ec.europa.eu/waterportal	The JRC water portal serves as the gateway to JRC's products on freshwater and marine water resources, providing access to water data, publications, and maps, as well as to water projects and events.

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Jupiter (Denmark's geological and hydrological database)	http://www.geus.dk/UK/data-maps/jupiter/Pages/default.aspx	Jupiter is GEUS' nationwide database for groundwater, drinking water, raw materials, environmental and geotechnical data. The database is the common public database within the field and is part of Denmark's Environment Portal.
Open Water Data Initiative	https://www.fgdc.gov/initiatives/open-water-data-initiative	Maintained by the US Federal Geographic Data Committee, the OWDI seeks to integrate currently fragmented water information into a connected, national water data framework by leveraging existing systems, infrastructure and tools to underpin innovation, modeling, data sharing, and solution development.
Swiss Federal Office of the Environment (FOEN) – topic water	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water.html	Entry point for information on flow, monitoring data, status of water bodies, groundwater data
Swiss Federal Office of the Environment (FOEN) – Water: Monitoring Data	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/state/data.html	Entry point for information on monitoring data and statistics
USGS Water Data for the Nation	https://waterdata.usgs.gov/nwis	Entry point provided by the US Geological Survey for data on water flow and levels, water quality and water use data in the US.
Water Information System for Europe	http://water.europa.eu/data-and-themes	The Water Data Centre, hosted at the European Environment Agency (EEA), provides a central access point to several web-services: interactive maps, data viewers, European datasets and indicators. The Water Statistics website, hosted at Eurostat, gives access to the results of the reporting from countries to the Eurostat/OECD Joint Questionnaire on Inland Waters.
Water Isotope System for Data Analysis, Visualization, and Electronic Retrieval	http://www-naweb.iaea.org/napc/ih/IHS_resources_isohis.html	WISER is a self-service platform for data of the Global Networks of Isotopes in Precipitation (GNIP) and Rivers (GNIR), hosted within the IAEA's repository for technical resources (NUCLEUS).
WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation	https://www.wssinfo.org/	Entry point for data files and country reports for data collected to support the MDGs on water and sanitation and for data to be collected for SDG 6.1 and 6.2.
WMO Hydrological Observing System	http://www.wmo.int/pages/prog/hwrp/chy/whos/	WHOS is the portal to the online holdings of National Hydrological Services (NHS) around the world that publish their historical (OBS) and/or real-time (RT) data without restrictions or cost. It represents the hydrological component of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS).

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World Hydrological Cycle Observing System	http://www.whycos.org/whycos/	WHYCOS is a framework programme of the WMO dedicated to improving basic observation activities, strengthening international cooperation and promoting the free exchange of data in the field of hydrology.